

Phase Behavior and New Applications of Hyperbranched Polymers in the Field of Chemical Engineering

Dissertation / Ph.D. Thesis by
Matthias Seiler

University of Erlangen-Nuremberg
Technische Fakultät der Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg

Erlangen, Germany **August 2004**

Source:

Published by **Fortschritt-Berichte VDI, Reihe 3, Nr. 820 (August 2004)**

Further details can be found in the aforementioned Ph.D. thesis or in:
Fluid Phase Equilibria: Volume 241, Issues 1–2, March 2006, Pages 155-174